

A Study on Neikuri in Hypertension

S. Mohamed Ajmal

UG Scholar, Sivaraj Siddha
Medical College, Salem,
Tamilnadu, India

M. Nagalakshmi

UG Scholar, Sivaraj Siddha
Medical College, Salem,
Tamilnadu, India

A. Raja Rajeswari

Lecturer, Department of Noi
Naadal, Sivaraj Siddha Medical
College, Salem, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

The methodology of diagnosis in Siddha system is based on eight fold examinations of pulse, reflex, tongue, body color and complexion, speech, eyes and sight, stools and urine. Of all these parameters, Urine examination has gained paramount importance next to pulse examination. Neikuri is a diagnostic tool of urine examination using Sesame seed oil developed by Siddhars and also throws a light on prognosis of disease condition. This is an attempt to understand the Siddha system of diagnosing pathological conditions which are a non-invasive, highly cost effective procedure which can be used for both diagnostic and prognostic purposes. This study aims to validate the Neikuri image on the patients diagnosed as Hypertension. For the purpose of the study, ten urine samples of Hypertension patients were collected and the oil drop test was conducted using the guidelines mentioned the Siddha Literature. Majority of samples showed a ring shape like circle under Iyam humor. This study can be used as referenced diagnostic criteria for Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Siddha system of medicine is a traditional medical system has been practiced in India for 2000 years. Vali, Azhal, Iyam are the three humors and their equilibrium disturbances produces pathological states.[1] The diagnosis in siddha system of medicine is based on eight fold examination methods like, (Naadi, Naa, Niram, Mozhi, Vizhi, Sparism, Malam, Moothiram (Neerkuri and Neikuri). Of these Neikuri(oil drop test) is important[2]. It is used for diagnosis and prognostic purposes. Neikuri is done in

patient urine is collected in a vessel, a drop of sesame oil is placed over and spreading of oil drop on the urine surface is noted[3]. The present study was planned to validate the Siddha diagnostic procedure (Neikuri) in Hypertension. The study was carried out to validate the Neikuri for Hypertension.

Materials and Methods

Neikuri

Sterile plastic container for urine collection, round glass bowl, toothpick, urine of patients, sesameseed oil.

Selection of patients

Total number of 10 patients of Hypertension were taken for this study. For this study 25 patients were screened from the out patients of Sivaraj Siddha Medical College, Salem, Tamilnadu.

Criteria for inclusion

Age 20 to 60, patients having only Hypertension were consider for selection.

Collection of urine sample

The methodology for the collection of urine sample from the patients mentioned in the literature was strictly followed. On the day before, selected patients were advised to eat six tastes of food and were asked to sleep well. On the next day early morning they were asked to collect the urine sample in the provided 100 ml container [4].

Urine examination with oil drop

A 50ml of urine is collected in a sterile plastic container and transformed in to a round glass bowl and kept on a flat surface without disturbing. A drop

of sesame oil was dropped at the center over the surface of urine in a round glass bowl by using a toothpick at a distance of 6cm height from the urine

surface. The pattern of oil spread was keenly observe under sunlight at 0, 30, 60 seconds. The observations are noted diagrammatically and inference is noted.

S.NO	Blood pressure (mmHg)	Image of oil spread over the surface				Pattern of oil Spread	Inferences related with Humours
		0 second	15 seconds	30 seconds	60 seconds		
1	150/110		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
2	150/110		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
3	140/110		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
4	150/110		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
5	150/110		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
6	160/120		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl			
7	170/120		Pitha vaatham	On the surface of urine the oil spread slowly and form a ring shape and beak appearance.			
8	170/120		Pitha vaatham	On the surface of oil drop spread medium like a ring elongated as irregular pattern.			
9	160/120		Pitham	On the surface of oil drop spread medium like a ring as irregular pattern.			
10	150/100		Kabham	On the surface of urine oil drop stays as pearl,			

Results and Discussion

In traditional system of medicine Neikuri an oil drop test in urine is a cost effective diagnostic procedure carried out to rule out the diseased condition. By the mode of spread of oil in the urine, diagnoses are made. Neikuri is based on the consistency, thickness, density of urine and the interfacial tension and viscous forces play a major role. The procedure of spreading pattern of oil on urine and the interpretation of the outcomes are clearly mentioned by Theraiyar in the literature of Siddha and it is discussed below. If the oil drop takes the shape of a snake, it indicates the body is Vali humors. If it spreads like a ring it indicates Azhal and if it stands like a pearl it indicates Iyam humours. These spread patterns indicates normal physiological state. If there is a combined shape like a ring in a snake or snake in ring, snake and a pearl or a pearl in the ring. The results of table 1 show that among ten patients diagnosed as Hypertension, majority of Neikuri 80% interpreted the image of Pearl. The Pearl shaped pattern of the oil drop indicates the patients were predominantly under Iyam humor. This signs indicates that the patients were not in normal physiological state.

Conclusion

From the above results, it is concluded that the oil drop stands like a pearl and produce the image of Pearl shape might be one of the diagnostic feature of the Hypertension disease. The present study was a preliminary to ascertain the mode of oil spread in urine of Hypertension patients. In future, large number of samples will be studied to standardize this oil drop test in various diseased patients.

References

1. Uthamarayan C.S. Siddha MaruthuvangaChurukkam. 2nded. Chennai:Department of Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy; 2006.
2. Shanmugavelu M. NoinaadalmudhalnaadalThiratu. Part I. Chennai: Department of Indian Medicine and Homeopathy; 2003. p. 269.
3. Shanmugavelu M. NoinaadalmudhalnaadalThiratu. Part I. Chennai: Department of Indian Medicine and Homeopathy; 2003. p. 282.
4. Ramachandran S.P. Therayarneerkurivaithiyam, neerkurinool – neikurinool, moolamumuraiyum. 2nd ed Chennai: Thamarainoolagam 2015.